

PEPPER: Profiling-based Edge Placement and Partitioning for Deep Learning Execution

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Abstract

Unlocking the full potential of AI at the edge requires overcoming the fundamental challenge of running complex models efficiently on devices with limited computational power. In this work, the challenge of optimizing the deployment of deep learning models in resource-constrained environments is addressed. A novel pipeline is proposed for profiling and partitioning ONNX models, to enhance inference efficiency across heterogeneous hardware platforms. Optimal split points within the deep learning models are identified through the application of Tarjan’s Bridge-Finding Algorithm, and the inference times of the models are predicted per device based on the respective characteristics and CPU load. For the prediction of inference times, the XGBoost algorithm is employed. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is validated through experiments conducted on real-world edge devices, demonstrating that highly efficient and adaptable deployment of complex deep learning models can be achieved in such environments.

Keywords

Profiling, Distributed Inference, Edge, Placement, IoT

1 Introduction

In recent years, deep learning has rapidly advanced, becoming the backbone of a variety of Internet of Things (IoT) applications that extend to almost all research and business fields. Traditionally,

deep learning algorithms have been deployed on powerful central computing systems for on-cloud processing, due to their high computational demands. This approach subsequently results in further issues, such as high network latency, which is a prohibitive factor for real-time applications, while also raising concerns about the privacy and safety of user data. As such, there has been an ongoing effort to move from a centralized cloud to an edge computing paradigm [3], i.e. processing data close to their source, thereby reducing the high latencies associated with transferring data to the cloud. Consumer-grade edge devices such as NVIDIA Jetson and Raspberry Pi are widely adopted in a variety of applications in the domains of agriculture, healthcare, industry [1, 24, 25], due to their relatively low cost and low power consumption.

However, running computationally intensive tasks on edge devices presents significant challenges due to their limited processing capabilities. These constraints often hinder the direct deployment of AI models on such devices. To address this issue, two widely recognized approaches have emerged: **split computing** and **distributed inference**. These methodologies aim to reduce the computational load on edge devices by dividing the processing tasks between the edge and more powerful servers (e.g., in the cloud), or among edge devices, thereby enabling more efficient and feasible execution of AI workloads in resource-constrained environments.

Efficient orchestration in heterogeneous distributed environments requires tools capable of analyzing and classifying computational tasks according to their complexity, distinguishing between

lightweight and heavyweight workloads. Accurate classification is essential for deciding whether a task should be executed at the edge or in the cloud. To enable effective decision-making, these tools require a certain level of built-in intelligence. In this context, profilers serve as key enablers. By analyzing performance metrics such as CPU usage, memory consumption, and latency, profilers offer detailed insights on the resource demands of each task. These insights enable orchestration systems to intelligently partition workloads and distribute them across available resources, optimizing both performance and efficiency in heterogeneous computing environments.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- **A framework-agnostic partitioning pipeline:** We introduce a model partitioning methodology built on the ONNX (Open Neural Network Exchange) [40] standard, enabling seamless interoperability and deployment of deep learning models across heterogeneous edge and cloud environments.
- **Adaptive placement guided by real-time profiling:** We propose a deployment strategy that dynamically allocates submodels based on online profiling of device characteristics and instantaneous computational load, ensuring efficient utilization of constrained resources.
- **Inference-time-centric profiling:** We shift the focus of distributed inference optimization from purely communication-driven metrics to profiling based on actual submodel inference time, demonstrating that execution-aware profiling can significantly enhance distributed AI performance.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature and introduces the main terminology of the field. Section 3 details the proposed processing pipeline that first splits the model and then profiles its sub-models based on the underlying hardware. Section 4 describes the experimental setup that evaluates the feasibility and performance of the proposed pipeline. Finally, Section 5 discusses the impact of our work on the broader research landscape.

2 Related Work

2.1 Distributed Inference

The optimization of AI models for deployment on edge devices has attracted significant research interest, driven by the exponential growth of Machine and Deep Learning applications. Various approaches have been proposed, ranging from the implementation of specialized hardware tailored to model’s specifications, to algorithmic techniques such as quantization and pruning, and extending to high-level solutions like collaborative and distributed inference. Distributed inference refers to partitioning the inference computation for execution across different devices, thereby reducing the computational cost. The work of [21] considers two distinct approaches: *data-distributed* and *model-distributed* inference. In data-distributed inference (DDI), an end-user partitions input data to be processed by separate workers, which may include edge devices and/or cloud servers. A recent example is the work of [46] which presents “ELF”, a framework that uses an LSTM-based Deep Neural Network (DNN) to generate region proposals from video frames, which are clustered and offloaded to edge servers for computer vision tasks. Due to data transmission and the necessity for every worker to store a copy of

the DNN model to run the inference, data-distributed approaches entail high communication and memory cost.

On the other hand, model-distributed inference (MDI) partitions the DNN among the available devices, offering a more efficient solution while simultaneously introducing higher complexity. Two subcategories of methods can be further distinguished: splitting a model horizontally or vertically. A horizontal (or sequential) split partitions the model between layers, creating subgroups of consecutive layers and assigning each subgroup to a device. On the contrary, a vertical (or parallel) split partitions a layer, creating sublayers that can be executed independently on different devices. The work of [36] investigates different partitioning schemes for Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) layers to reduce computation costs, introducing Layer Output Partitioning (LOP) and Layer Input Partitioning (LIP) as two complementary methods. These are further combined in a parallelized approach called FUSE, which eliminates the need for intermediate concatenation and merging. An ILP algorithm is employed to optimize partitioning by minimizing data transmission delays. Applied to YOLOv2 [31], FUSE achieved consistent inference speedups across various hardware and network configurations.

In [47] an alternative approach to vertically splitting CNNs is introduced, named Fused Tile Partitioning (FTP), which is integrated in the DeepThings framework, a hybrid DDI-MDI approach. FTP partitions every convolutional and pooling layer into a grid and the respective tiles in consecutive layers are fused together, effectively forming multiple parallel execution tasks and therefore reducing the memory footprint significantly. DeeperThings [35] simultaneously builds upon the approaches introduced in [36], [47], by using an FTP-based approach and combining with an improved partitioning method for fully-connected layers. In addition, a new ILP algorithm was developed to optimize communication, computation and memory cost, by determining the optimal point to switch from feature map partitioning to weight partitioning, as well as the optimal split for the fully connected layers.

A common distributed inference setup involves one or more edge devices and a cloud server, among which the computation is shared. Such an approach is introduced in [18]. The proposed method, named “Neurosurgeon”, intelligently partitions a target DNN to offload inference between the cloud and edge based on the DNN’s topology, datacenter load, wireless network uplink bandwidth and power consumption. Neurosurgeon operates in two phases: during deployment, the framework trains regression models to predict the per-layer latency of a DNN using standard DNN layer types like convolutional, pooling and fully connected layers, arranged in various configurations. During runtime, Neurosurgeon uses the regressors to estimate the latency and energy consumption of the DNN’s layers when executed on both the cloud and the mobile/edge device, while also considering data center load and wireless network characteristics.

Despite its simplicity and effectiveness, Neurosurgeon can only handle DNNs with a simple chain topology, which hinders its applicability as state-of-the-art DNNs become more complex. The authors of [45] propose a method to dynamically split a deep neural network with a DAG (Directed Acyclic Graph) topology, where the nodes of the DNN are the vertices of the graph and the edges represent the data flow from one node to another. A latency graph

is constructed from the DNN, where each node is linked to two edges representing cloud and edge execution latency, and additional edges capture the data transmission latency between layers. Thus, the model splitting task is reduced to a min-cut problem of the constructed latency graph. To this purpose, a two-stage algorithm is defined, named QDMP (quick deep model partition). In the first stage, the latency graph is converted to an undirected graph, and Tarjan’s algorithm for identifying bridges [39] is applied to it. Vertices forming each bridge constitute the graph’s cut vertex set—nodes whose removal results in two disjoint subgraphs. Applying Tarjan’s algorithm at this initial stage effectively reduces the solution search space. In the second stage, QDMP iterates all pairs of the vertex cut set and finds the min-cut of the subgraph between them, i.e. the vertex set that minimizes the latency. The authors compare their approach against contemporary model splitting approaches, namely the Neurosurgeon approach described above, and DADS [16], a graph-theoretic approach similar to QDMP. The evaluation, conducted on a range of state-of-the-art DNNs across diverse setups (edge-only, cloud-only, 3G/4G networks) and heterogeneous hardware (Raspberry Pi and x86 desktops), showed that QDMP consistently outperformed existing methods in latency and decision time. However, its inability to handle graphs featuring cycles limits its applicability to modern architectures such as Visual Transformers.

The horizontal MDI methods presented in the previous paragraphs all considered a single split of the DNN graph, with the resulting subgraphs distributed between two devices. These approaches are not applicable to real-world scenarios, where the number of edge devices increases dramatically. In contrast, the authors of [11] introduce a fully automated, flexible approach for supporting CNN distributed inference across multiple edge devices, avoiding dependency on the cloud. The major component of the proposed framework is a tool named AutoDice, which, given a pre-trained CNN in ONNX format, along with a layer-device mapping and a specification of the available computing resources, splits the model and automatically generates efficient, cross-platform C++ code for the execution of the submodels. The framework employs a multi-stage design-space exploration approach using a two-level genetic algorithm to optimize throughput, memory, and energy across heterogeneous processing elements. While platform-agnostic and scalable, it has limited fault tolerance and relatively high deployment times, making it less suitable for time-sensitive applications.

The methods discussed above highlight the key role of AI model profiling with respect to various factors, including computation, memory and communication cost, for the realization of effective distributed inference strategies. In the next subsection, several profiling approaches are presented.

2.2 Profiling

Recent years have seen a surge in profiling AI models to optimize their execution on edge devices. This increased interest stems from the need to deploy AI capabilities directly on resource-constrained hardware, enabling efficient and responsive AI applications in various real-world scenarios.

Florian’s study in [8] examined smart home ML applications, face and speech recognition, focusing on how input size, model

complexity, and system load affect performance and resource use. They used edge-optimized frameworks: Vosk en-us 0.22-lgraph and 0.15-small for speech, and MobileFaceNet [5], FaceNet [33], ArcResFaceNet for face recognition. Experiments were conducted on datasets with varying input sizes (Google Speech Commands, LibriSpeech, LFW) using a Raspberry Pi 4B and a desktop PC (Ryzen 5 3600, RTX 3070). The results indicated that larger input sizes and more complex models led to increased CPU usage and latency, with the Raspberry Pi 4B exhibiting significantly higher performance degradation under load.

Optimizing edge data streaming often hinges on effective profiling. Geren et al. [9] introduced a profiling method that predicts processing times of stream processing operators across diverse hardware by considering each device’s CPU clock speed. They also proposed a performance model using Integer Linear Programming (ILP) to estimate the maximum input rate a system can handle and identify bottlenecks, enabling optimal operator placement. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed methods, with the profiling approach achieving an average error of only 5% in processing time predictions. The performance model accurately estimates maximum input rates and significantly improves throughput (up to 257%) and latency (up to 70%) compared to Apache Storm’s default scheduler.

However, profiling is also essential for distributed inference. Parra-Ullauri et al. [27] proposed a profiling and optimization method for AI models on edge devices. Their approach runs models on diverse devices to collect resource usage data, which is used to train predictors—preferably via Federated Learning—for estimating resource demands. They apply Deep Reinforcement Learning to decide model layer offloading and emphasize monitoring, offloading policies, and link quality. As profilers, XGBoost [6] and MLPs were used, with XGBoost achieving a notably low RMSE of 0.001.

Lu et al. [23] investigated the minimum hardware requirements for Deep Learning on mobile devices. They achieved this by deploying and analyzing popular CNNs (AlexNet [20], VGG-16 [34], GoogleNet [37], ResNet-50 [12]) on mobile CPUs and GPUs, meticulously measuring per-layer performance and resource consumption to identify optimization opportunities. They also developed models to predict resource needs for CNN computations. Their work resulted in Augur, a profiling tool that estimates CNN compute time and resource usage based on model configuration, offering insights into its mobile platform feasibility and efficiency. The profiling focused on timing—via full forward passes, per-layer execution, and FLOPs—and memory usage, distinguishing parameter, intermediate, and workspace memory.

As demonstrated by Viramontes et al. [42], profilers are capable of predicting various performance metrics, such as latency, through approaches like DIME (Distributed Inference Model Estimation), an ILP-based method for distributed DNN inference. DIME profiles bundle latencies to guide layer partitioning and assignment across edge devices. Experiments on AlexNet and VGG11 involved devices with different bandwidths, including a LePotato (edge), NVIDIA 2080TI (cloud), and Jetson Nano (intermediate hub). DIME adjusted the Maximum Bundle Size (MBS) to balance profiling effort and accuracy. It consistently matched actual latency values and identified optimal layer assignments, even in setups with varied network conditions and hardware.

Xue et al. [44] developed EdgeLD, a distributed DNN inference framework for edge clusters following a MapReduce-like paradigm. A designated Group Leader (GL) handles data storage and model partitioning, while Follower Nodes (FNs) perform parallel computation. Linear regression models estimate convolution and transmission times for task allocation. Evaluated on VGG13 and VGG16 across virtual machines, EdgeLD achieved up to $3.57\times$ speedups with increased FNs and high-bandwidth settings. However, excessive input frames reduced performance due to memory and I/O constraints.

DNN profiling tools often suffer from high overhead and poor correlation between model design and hardware performance, as noted by Wu et al. [43]. To overcome these issues, they propose PProof, a lightweight framework that links hardware metrics to model layers and supports layer fusion. It avoids reliance on hardware performance counters by employing analytical models to estimate FLOPs and memory access. PProof runs as a CLI tool that takes ONNX models, widely supported across major deep learning frameworks, and a backend as input, producing performance metrics viewable through an intuitive dataviewer for optimization guidance.

Compared to the above works, our approach goes beyond existing distributed inference strategies by jointly addressing model partitioning, profiling, and execution in a unified framework specifically designed for multi-device, federated, and resource-constrained environments. Furthermore, in contrast to conventional profiling methods that focus mainly on inference cost prediction, we integrate profiling into the decision-making loop for layer assignment, incorporating communication patterns, memory constraints, and device availability. Finally, our framework natively supports more complex DAG-based architectures and provides resilience to device variability. This results in a more flexible and scalable distributed inference pipeline capable of adapting to real-world multi-edge scenarios where conditions and workloads are highly dynamic.

3 Methodology

This paper introduces an AI optimizer pipeline, called PEPPER – Profiling-based Edge Placement and Partitioning for Deep Learning Execution – that is illustrated in Figure 1 and is responsible for deploying ONNX models across ARM-based device clusters such as NVIDIA Jetson and Raspberry Pi boards. The system initially receives an ONNX model that is fed to a Model Characteristics Extractor (MCE) and a Model Splitter. The Model Splitter partitions the initial model into n submodels, which are then fed into the MCE. The MCE is responsible for extracting model/submodel specifications, e.g., number of convolutional, fully connected, and pooling layers). Then, the Profiler takes as input the model(s) specifications and the resource characteristics of the cluster (e.g., CPU current load, disk usage, and device type) that consists of a varying number of edge devices. Finally, the Profiler decides where to place the model(s) and run the inference tasks for optimal execution. It is worth noting that the AI optimizer can also deploy a single ONNX model without partitioning it, therefore the Model Splitter is optional and is utilized only if the system user decides to do so. The idea behind this approach is that the Model Splitter will be employed if the original model does not fit into a single cluster device or if the time taken to run the inference task of a model will

be reduced when running its respective submodels based on the available resources.

3.1 Distributed Inference Algorithm

The first part of the proposed approach is the Model Splitter. A model-distributed horizontal approach was developed to automatically identify critical connection points in the DNN computation graph as potential splitting points, using Tarjan’s algorithm for bridge detection. A bridge is defined as an edge whose removal will result in increasing the number of connected components in the graph; in other words, it partitions the graph. Intuitively, the algorithm is well suited to the problem, as identifying loose connections highlights distinct processing stages within the DNN. Moreover, it uncovers bridges in linear time, which motivates its use in edge distributed systems, where efficiency is vital. Previous works such as the QDMP algorithm [45] have used Tarjan’s algorithm to shrink the search space for the optimal splitting solution.

An initial preprocessing takes place in order to transform all model graphs into a homogeneous format that can be utilized by our pipeline. Namely, 1) the DNN, represented in ONNX format, is loaded and the model graph is modified to not include nodes with blank names, 2) when applicable, initializer nodes (non-user-defined input nodes, such as weights and biases) are appended to the ONNX graph input to enable correct submodel extraction with ONNX routines, 3) a GraphML representation of the ONNX model is generated to enable manipulation of the graph with the Python NetworkX library¹.

In the main module, the graph is converted to an undirected equivalent, and the NetworkX implementation of Tarjan’s algorithm is applied. The bridges are then filtered to exclude potential split points that include unnecessary operation types or whose removal would compromise the subgraph’s integrity, such as initializer nodes. Subsequently, the shortest path distances from the input node to the output node for every node in the graph are calculated, and every bridge is assigned to its respective depth. The bridges are further filtered to retain only those points that are reasonably spaced apart, thereby avoiding the creation of trivial or redundant subgraphs. The resulting split points are then used with the ONNX library model slicing utilities, and the resulting submodels are automatically stored in the specified path. The validity of the split is ensured by comparing the inference result between the original non-distributed model and its partitioned counterpart. The algorithm was applied to state-of-the-art DNNs for computer vision tasks featuring varying topologies, ranging from simple chain structures such as AlexNet and ResNet to more complex DAGs like GoogleNet and DeepLab [4]. Table 1 provides the full list of evaluated models.

The output of this step in the pipeline is the partitioned DNNs. These submodels are then used in the profiling step that follows.

3.2 Profiler

To achieve an optimized placement of AI models/submodels to the available edge devices, a profiling mechanism needs to be employed. The proposed profiler is designed to predict the inference time of deep learning models and/or their respective submodels, and acts

¹<https://networkx.org/>

Figure 1: Model profiling and partitioning architecture

Figure 2: Input and output of the Profiler

as an assistant for the model splitting mechanism. Specifically, the profiler employs an XGBoost model to perform regression analysis. XGBoost was selected for this regression task due to its proven effectiveness in handling structured data with heterogeneous feature types, its capability to capture complex non-linear relationships through gradient-boosted decision trees, and its high computational efficiency [2, 7, 10], making it well-suited for regression problems where accurate and fast inference time prediction is critical.

The profiler takes as input features related to both the model and the device to predict the inference time of the given model (see Figure 2). Model-related inputs include the number of convolutional layers, fully connected layers, pooling layers, and the total number of parameters. Device-related inputs consist of current CPU usage, and disk usage. Additionally, the input features also include the model’s input size (e.g., the size of the input image). It is worth noting that the output size of the current submodel is equal to the input size of the next submodel.

To train the XGBoost model, a dataset was generated from various state-of-the-art models for core computer vision tasks (image classification, object detection, 6D pose estimation), which use the ONNX format, and their segmented variants produced by the algorithm described in Section 3.1, incorporating the aforementioned features. The experiments were carried out on two host devices, a

Raspberry Pi and a Jetson Nano, where the selected models were executed and relevant metrics were collected using a profiling script. (see Figure 3).

We opted to include various representative CNNs with diverse architectures that are widely applied to image classification and object detection tasks, namely AlexNet, DenseNet-121 [17], EfficientNet-Lite4 [38], GoogleNet (v1), MobileNet-v2 [15], ResNet-152, and VGG-16. The models are publicly available in the ONNX GitHub repository². Additionally, we utilized the DeepLabv3+ [4] encoder-decoder model integrated in the EPOS [13] framework for 6D pose estimation. Using a single DeepLab instance, EPOS is able to detect and localize multiple objects featuring challenging characteristics in complex scenes, achieving competitive performance in the BOP 2020 Challenge [14]. EPOS was chosen as it is representative of instance-based methods, which are established in the 6D pose estimation domain. Finally, we included the PyTorch [28] implementations of the more recent RegNet [30] and ConvNeXt [22] architectures, as well as the Keras³ implementation of NASNet-Large [48], after transforming them to the ONNX format. Most of the aforementioned models are pretrained to accept input images of size 224×224, with the exception of DeepLab which accepts images

²<https://github.com/onnx/models>

³<https://keras.io/>

Figure 3: Collection of metrics and creation of the dataset

Table 1: Model Architecture Characteristics

Model	ONNX version	Conv Layers	FC Layers	Pooling Layers
AlexNet	1.9	5	3	3
DenseNet-121	1.9	121	1	5
EfficientNet-Lite4	1.7.0	91	1	1
GoogLeNet (v1)	1.9	57	1	14
MobileNet-v2	1.2.1	54	1	1
ResNet-152	1.2.1	155	1	2
VGG-16	1.2.1	13	3	5
DeepLabv3	1.10.0	149	1	1
RegNet	1.18.0	74	1	1
ConvNeXT	1.18.0	40	73	1
NasNetLarge	1.17.0	488	1	57

of size 640 x 480. To introduce more variation and better capture the impact of the input size on inference time, the NASNetLarge model was modified to accept 640x360 input dimensions, consistent with the original image resolution of the Animal Kingdom dataset. The models selected for the experiments are listed in Table 1. It should be noted that the PyTorch and TensorFlow ONNX exporter routines⁴ apply various optimizations on the model graph such as node fusion, constant folding and node elimination [29], before exporting to the final ONNX format. Since the layer characteristics reported in 1 are derived from the ONNX models directly, there may be differences (e.g. in layer count) compared to the literature.

⁴<https://github.com/pytorch/pytorch/blob/main/torch/onnx/utils.py>,
⁵<https://github.com/onnx/tensorflow-onnx/tree/main/tf2onnx/optimizer>

Since most of the models (with the exception of DeepLab) were pretrained for animal detection, the Animal Kingdom dataset [26] was used during inference. On the other hand, DeepLab was trained on IndustryShapes [32], an RGB-D dataset of industrial tools and components to benchmark 6D pose estimation approaches. From each dataset, 100 images were randomly sampled from the respective test sets, and inference was run 100 times per model per device to build the profiling dataset. DeepLab exhibited the highest computational demand, with inference times ranging from 20 to 30 seconds. RegNet, ConvNeXt, and NASNetLarge also demonstrated elevated inference times, on the order of a few seconds, exceeding those of the remaining models that demonstrated inference times of only a few milliseconds. The produced dataset also includes profiling data for partitioned models generated via Tarjan’s algorithm (see Section 3.1).

The “device type” attribute of the dataset was transformed from a categorical feature into a numerical representation due to XGBoost’s limited native support for categorical variables. A value of 0 denotes a Raspberry Pi 4B, while a value of 1 indicates a Jetson Nano. To prepare the dataset for training, normalization and encoding techniques were applied. Numerical features were scaled using MinMaxScaler⁵ to a fixed range, typically [0, 1], ensuring that each feature contributes proportionally to the learning process. Categorical variables were converted to binary vectors using OneHotEncoder⁶, enabling proper interpretation by the regression model.

During the inference phase for each model, the stress-ng⁷ CPU stress tool was utilized to impose load on the device. The number of CPU cores utilized by the stress tool and the applied load percentage varied across executions. To normalize the device load relative to the baseline hardware capacity, the load is calculated in the preprocessing step as:

$$\text{device_load_percent} = \frac{\text{stresser_device_cpu_cores} \times \text{stresser_load_percent}}{4}$$

Here, stresser_device_cpu_cores represents the number of cores under load during the execution, and stresser_load_percent is the load percentage per stressed core. The denominator corresponds to the total number of logical CPU cores available on the baseline devices used in this work, such as the Raspberry Pi 4B or Jetson Nano. This formula effectively converts the load measured per core into an overall device-wide load percentage, normalized against the total CPU capacity. The Profiler is specifically trained on CPU usage values that fall below 35% or exceed 65%, focusing on these ranges to better capture low and high load conditions while avoiding ambiguous mid-range values that could introduce noise or uncertainty into the model’s predictions.

4 Evaluation

In this section, a series of experiments is presented to demonstrate the effectiveness of the developed model. These experiments are conducted to rigorously evaluate the model’s performance under

⁵<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.preprocessing.MinMaxScaler.html>

⁶<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.preprocessing.OneHotEncoder.html>

⁷<https://manpages.ubuntu.com/manpages/focal/man1/stress-ng.1.html>

various conditions. During metric collection and dataset creation, the selected models demonstrated distinct performance levels. As previously stated, each model was executed 100 times using the CPU in both the Raspberry Pi 4B and Jetson Nano scenarios. The Profiler was trained on the previously described dataset. Testing revealed that lightweight models with fast inference times were unsuitable candidates for inclusion in the dataset; the difference in the inference times of those models was negligible, e.g., only a few milliseconds, and a clear distinction under varying device CPU load was not present. Accurate inference time prediction required the Profiler to be trained on more complex models with longer inference durations that pose significant variations in the inference time under varying device CPU loads. DeepLab, RegNet, ConvNeXt, NASNetLarge, and the submodels of DeepLab demonstrate substantially longer inference times relative to the other DNNs.

To deploy the proposed model in real-world scenarios, it is essential to validate the reliability of its outputs. Accordingly, ten-fold cross-validation was employed to assess the model's generalization performance. The best-performing model was identified based on the results of the evaluation process and achieved performance. The following metrics were used to assess the models' performance:

- (1) Mean Absolute Error (MAE): Represents the average absolute difference between predicted and actual values. A value close to 0 indicates high prediction accuracy.
- (2) Mean Squared Error (MSE): Calculates the average of the squared differences between predicted and actual values. It emphasizes larger errors due to the squaring, making it more sensitive to outliers.
- (3) Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): The square root of MSE, expressing the error in the same unit as the target variable. Like MSE, it penalizes larger errors more heavily.
- (4) R-squared (R^2) Score: Indicates the proportion of variance in the target variable that is explained by the model. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 denotes a perfect fit and 0 means the model explains none of the variance. Negative values imply poor model performance.

Figure 4: MAE result

The model demonstrated strong predictive performance based on several evaluation metrics. The results of the best-performing XGBoost model of the 10-fold cross validation can be seen in Figure

4. It achieved a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.5727, indicating that, on average, the model's predictions deviated from the actual target values by approximately 0.5565 units. This metric provides a straightforward interpretation of prediction accuracy, unaffected by the direction of errors. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) was 0.6927, which further quantifies prediction accuracy but penalizes larger errors more heavily due to the squaring of residuals, making it particularly sensitive to outliers. The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) was 0.8323, providing an interpretable measure of the model's typical prediction error on the same scale as the target variable, which helps in understanding the magnitude of prediction deviations more intuitively. In terms of variance explanation, the model achieved a high coefficient of determination (R^2 score) of 0.9934, meaning that it accounts for approximately 99.34% of the variability in the target variable. This high R^2 value indicates that the model provides an excellent fit to the data and captures the underlying trends effectively.

Collectively, these metrics suggest that the Profiler is not only accurate on average (low MAE and RMSE) but also robust to large errors (low MSE), and capable of capturing nearly all variance in the data (high R^2). This strong performance across multiple dimensions indicates that the model generalizes well to the problem at hand and is well-suited for making precise predictions of inference time. To assess the model's predictive accuracy, Figure 5 presents a visual comparison between the actual and predicted values. The close alignment of these values across the dataset indicates that the model captures the underlying patterns effectively.

Figure 5: Predicted vs Actual values

After identifying the best-performing model for profiling through a ten-fold cross-validation, tests were carried out in a real environment. Each of the selected resource-intensive models (distributed or not) was deployed on two Raspberry Pi 4B devices and one Jetson Nano, with inference performed 100 times while a varying CPU stressor was active. The Profiler was subsequently used to predict the inference time for each of the selected resource-intensive models across 100 runs per device, aiming to identify the device with the fastest execution. This enabled a direct comparison between the Profiler's predictions and the actual measured inference times.

In a second series of experiments, the Profiler’s predictive performance was evaluated against a baseline scenario in which models were randomly allocated to devices. To be considered reliable, the Profiler must consistently outperform random deployment strategies. As shown in Table 2, the Profiler achieved an accuracy of 98.63% in selecting the optimal device for the chosen resource-intensive models. Across all scenarios, it consistently outperformed random placement, which achieved only a 31.16% accuracy rate. These results highlight the effectiveness of the proposed profiling and splitting approach in facilitating informed and performance-aware device placement in heterogeneous execution environments.

Table 2: Average Placement Accuracy

PEPPER	Random Placement
98.63%	31.16%

5 Conclusions

This paper presented PEPPER, a pipeline that combines model splitting with a profiling method to enable efficient AI model placement across clusters of ARM-based devices, thus reducing the execution time of the AI models. The model splitter part of the pipeline utilizes a classic graph theory algorithm to uncover structurally significant connections between layers as potential splitting points. The model splitter was effectively applied to diverse DNN architectures, encompassing both chain and DAG topologies. Out of all models, ResNet produced the largest number of segments upon splitting, due to its relatively simple topology, characterized by a very deep, primarily chain-like structure with a few skip connections. On the other hand, models like GoogleNet possess a more complex topology, resulting in fewer submodels after splitting. The most challenging model was DeepLab, as its architecture features skip connections starting from the early layers and spanning most of the network’s length, therefore the algorithm only yielded a single possible split point.

Results from the Profiler experiments indicate that models with higher computational demands and longer inference times are predicted with greater accuracy. This outcome is intuitive, as models with already low inference times exert minimal load on the host hardware, thus completing the inference task in just a few milliseconds even when the CPU load is high. Due to their minimal resource consumption and short execution times, these models exhibit limited variability across devices, rendering profiling-based placement unnecessary. In contrast, heavier models significantly impact system performance, making accurate prediction of their behavior both more feasible and more valuable for effective deployment decisions.

Future research will focus on enhancing Tarjan’s algorithm by incorporating hardware-awareness tailored to the target deployment cluster. Additionally, the Profiler will be trained on datasets featuring more computationally intensive models to ensure reliable inference time predictions under heavier workloads. Plans are also in place to extend the Profiler with optimization parameters (e.g., profiling not only based on inference time but also on energy consumption or a combination of both). This functionality would

be especially beneficial for platforms like Greenkube [41], which orchestrate Kubernetes workloads based on energy efficiency. Integrating PEPPER architecture with Kubernetes presents an interesting direction, enabling the evaluation of its impact on orchestration and load distribution within a cluster. A key tool considered for these experiments is EdgeCloud Mon [19], a Prometheus-based monitoring solution that tracks the performance of containers and heterogeneous devices (x86 and ARM) within a Kubernetes environment.

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